

MSCA and Citizens 2023 Events 2024 QUESTIONNAIRE

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EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)

REA.A - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions & Support to Experts
A.4 - MSCA and citizens, COFUND, Global Postdoctoral Fellowships

Questionnaire on the European Researchers' Night - 2024 Edition and the Researchers at Schools activities carried out up to now

*** 1. Acronym of the project**

EU-EMBRACES

*** 2. Country of the event**

Portugal

*** 3. Location/s**

Alcanena, Braga, Bragança, Estremoz, Lagos, Lisboa, Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Oeiras, Porto

*** 4. Number of cities in which the event took place**

9

*** 5. Type of event**

- Full online
- Onsite
- Mix of online and onsite

6. In case it is a mix online-onsite give the approximate % of online and onsite activities:

AWARENESS CAMPAIGN

Which have been the most efficient actions in terms of reaching out to the target audiences?

7. Promotional material

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Folders
- Brochures
- Programmes
- Leaflets
- Posters
- Citylights
- Billboards
- Promotional video
- Advertisement in public spaces (squares, places, streets,...)
- Advertising on Radio - National
- Advertising on Radio - Local
- Advertising on TV - National
- Advertising on TV - Local
- Written media - Newspapers/Magazines
- Written media - Newsletters
- Written media - Other
- Written media at national level
- Written media at regional level

8. Project Website

- National
- Regional/local
- Links with other national or European websites

9. Social networks

- Facebook
- Twitter
- Flickr
- Instagram
- TikTok

Other

10. Press conference(s)

- At national level
 At regional/local level
 With other projects from the same country (if relevant)

Please keep a sample of the promotional material (posters, leaflets, programmes, gadgets...) You do not have to send it to us, unless you are requested to do so by your Project Officer.

RESEARCHERS AT SCHOOLS ACTIVITIES (online or onsite)

11. In the framework of your MSCA and Citizens project, have you organised Researchers at Schools Activities?

- Yes
 No

If "No" move to question 21, 'PRE-EVENTS' Section

If "Yes", please answer the following questions:

12. Type of event

- Full online
 Onsite
 Mix of online and onsite

13. How researchers at school activities have been organised?

14

14. Which type of schools:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Primary
 Secondary
 Other

If other (please specify)

15. (Approximately) how many students/pupils have been reached?

606

16. What kind of activities were offered:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Oral presentation
- Research collaborations
- Talks
- Hand-on experiments
- Questions and answers session
- Workshops
- Games
- Science kit for schools
- Marketplace activities
- Research seminars
- Science hacks
- Other

If other activities (please specify)

17. Area of activities:

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Chemistry
- Social Sciences and Humanities
- Economic Sciences
- Information Science and Engineering
- Environment and Geosciences
- Life Sciences
- Mathematics
- Physics
- Covid-19
- Other

If other area of activities (please specify)

18. Overall, how many researchers participated?

19. In the case that MSCA researchers were involved, how many participated?

20. Suggestions for the European Commission to improve the Researchers at Schools activities

Comments

We currently lack the ability to directly target researchers who benefit from MSCA funding (except for those directly associated with the consortium). This poses a challenge if maximizing the involvement of these researchers is a key objective for the European Commission.

PRE-EVENT(S)

21. How many pre-events have you organised?

If "0" move question 27 in the section 'Activities during the NIGHT'

22. What was the (typical) duration of a pre-event? (Number of days - If halfday encode 0.5)

23. What was the period when those pre-events were organised?

From

To

24. What was the nature of the pre-events:

- Online
- Onsite
- Hybrid (simultaneous onsite and online participation)

25. What kind of activities were offered during those pre-events:

- Hands-on activities and demonstrations
- Workshops
- Science shows
- Quizzes, escape rooms and challenges
- Informal talks, Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Open days and guided tours
- Theatre
- Other

Other pre-event(s) (please specify)

Bioblitz, Science Cafés, fieldwork activities, conferences, walking tour, bike rides, scientific picnic & tastings.

26. Type of Pre-event

- Flashmobs
- Teasing events in public places
- Teasing events at partners' premises
- Other

If other type of activities proposed during pre-event(s) (please specify)

ACTIVITIES DURING THE NIGHT

27. Type of activities organised

(Please click the relevant box(es))

- Hands-on activities
- Workshops
- Exhibitions
- Science shows
- Demonstrations
- Competitions
- Quizzes
- Informal talks/written chats, or Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Theatre
- Virtual Guided tours
- Other

Other (please specify)

Stand-up comedy, music and dance showcase, tastings, street art

28. Which were the most successful activities from a qualitative perspective? Please specify what were the topics addressed in these activities.

- Hands-on activities
- Workshops
- Exhibitions
- Science shows
- Demonstrations
- Competitions
- Quizzes
- Informal talks/written chats, or Q&A with researchers
- Games
- Theatre
- Virtual Guided tours

Please specify which topic/s for each of the activities ticked above:

Hands-on-activities: Human gyroscope, suspended bicycle (dynamical physics), plant biology, microbiology;
Workshops: Coral conservation, nutrition, sustainable agriculture;
Exhibitions: Cancer, microbiology;
Science shows: Chemistry;
Demonstrations: Food technology, lab-grown food, robotics, electric car, hydrogen car, electric and autonomous F1 car, hydroponics, biomaterials, artificial organs;
Competitions: Chemistry, microbiology;
Informal talks: Climate change, climate change throughout history, climate change through geology;
Games: epidemics, research method, antibiotic resistance;
Virtual guided tours: particle physics, cosmic ray, undersea conservation, boat tours.

RESEARCHERS INVOLVED

29. Total number of researchers involved in the activities organised

673

30. Number of researchers involved having benefitted from Marie Skłodowska-Curie schemes

7

31. Number of researchers involved having benefitted from EU support (FP7, H2020, HE) other than MSCA

161

ATTENDANCE AND OUTREACH

32. Overall number of attendees (whether possible, distributed by location)

4900

33. Estimate number of people made aware of the European Researchers' Night and its objectives

525000

34. If applicable, how did users rate the onsite experience?

- Very positive
- Positive
- Neutral
- Negative
- Very negative

35. What were the most usual feedbacks of the attendees/users about the onsite experience?

In terms of positive feedback, most participants appreciated the variety and diversity of the event offerings—such as the wide range of topics, the types of activities, and the tailoring of sessions for different audiences, including children, young people, and adults. The diversity of institutions and laboratories involved was also highly valued. The interactive nature of the activities, in particular, received significant praise. Additionally, many attendees appreciated the opportunity to engage directly with scientists, noting their availability, enthusiasm, clarity in explanations, and friendliness.

Additional positive feedback focused on the event's atmosphere. People noted the presence of many young participants (both among the organisers and scientists as well as among attendees) and felt that there was a strong sense of engagement and interest from all involved. Feedbacks appreciated the diversity of the audience, with joint participation from students and teachers, as well as parents and children.

Regarding critiques and suggestions for improvement, some attendees at smaller venues requested a greater variety of activities. While this feedback demonstrates audience interest, increasing variety in these venues is not always feasible due to resource constraints. Overall, there was also a call for broader event promotion. However, since events were extremely crowded throughout, many participants requested more space to accommodate the large number of visitors, along with suggestions to extend the event duration.

36. If applicable, how did users rate the online experience?

- Very positive
-

- Positive
- Neutral
- Negative
- Very negative

37. What were the most usual feedbacks of the attendees/users about the online experience?

COOPERATION WITH OTHER FUNDED PROJECTS

38. Cooperation with projects in your country

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify the acronym of these projects or number

We are unsure whether this question refers specifically to other ERN projects or, more broadly, to other European programs (such as MSCA, FP7, H2020, or Horizon Europe). If it is the former, we have not collaborated with any other consortia organizing ERN. If it is the latter, we can provide the acronym or project number of any European project from which researchers involved in our ERN initiative have benefitted.

39. Cooperation with projects in another (others) country(ies)

- Yes
- No

If yes, which projects in which country(ies)

40. Which type of cooperation?

- Awareness

- Common activities
- Exchange of researchers
- Real time connections
- Impact assessment
- Other

If other type of cooperation (please specify)

Please elaborate briefly on what was done in terms on cooperation

41. Have you involved the Marie Curie Alumni Association in your project activities?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was their role?

COMMENTS

42. Specific difficulties encountered and solutions identified

Comments

To overcome the challenge of covering an ERN event involving more than 40 institutions with footage and photos, one of the venues partnered with a vocational high school specialising in communication. This collaboration provided significant assistance in producing high-quality content and, at the same time, allowed a group of young people to participate in the NEI, many of whom had never attended this type of event before, thus further aligning with our goal of inclusivity.

To address the challenge of collecting a limited number of evaluation surveys from participants, we offered incentives (small tokens such as ERN tote bags). This strategy successfully increased the response rate for the surveys and also contributed to the promotion of the NEI beyond the event itself.

43. Aspects you would intend to modify during future editions

Comments

Some issues were identified on the website, so we plan to enhance the platform by updating the menu bar, adding interactive features, and redesigning the overall layout for a more user-friendly experience.

The involvement of multiple consortia (and associated institutions) organising simultaneous Researchers Night events with different visual identities and channels led to fragmented communication, especially in regions with more than one event. For future editions, we aim to encourage all consortia to cross-link or reference each other on their websites, fostering more unified, cohesive, and effective event communication.

Furthermore, for the next edition, we aim to have the complete program for the NEI available much earlier to improve dissemination and facilitate communication.

One of our venues is mostly outdoors, and while it offers a spacious and impressive setting that has been well-received by participants, it is prone to the risk of rain and wind, which could affect the success of the event. For next year, we are exploring the possibility of changing the location.

44. Suggestions for the European Commission with a view to future calls

Comments

Distributing EU promotional materials, such as flyers, brochures and postcards, to the consortium could be highly beneficial. These resources would complement the EU-Corner video streamed during the event, and further boost the EU's visibility. By providing these materials to partners, outreach efforts would be amplified, strengthening the EU's presence in key regions.

45. Any other issue that you would like to highlight

Thank you!

MSCA and Citizens Team

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Contact

[Contact Form](#)